

SELF-DYNAMIZATION WITHIN THE FORMAL GROUP IN THE ONLINE ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract

Purpose – Because digitalization is the foundation of a new era this paper proposes to make group work efficient in the online environment.

Methodology/approach - The issue of identifying psychosocial models for streamlining work teams in the online environment, regardless of the psychological profile of members involved, has become topical research.

Findings – Through the concept which we have developed, we want to introduce a cohesive workshop group model, specific to the online environment.

Research limitations/implications – Due to the current pandemic context, it has migrated to the online environment in all fields of activity.

Practical implications – The continuous development of Industry 4.0 have extended the boundaries of production, those of human relations but also those of knowledge. Since the onset of the pandemic and the strong entry into online meetings, the issue of integrating group workshops in the field of work, both in education and in the industry, has been stated.

Originality/value – We initiate a practical approach, for streamline group work in the online environment, and this can be achieved by combining individual skills with the requirement of the new social constructs.

Key words: Online environment, workshop group, pandemic context.

Introduction

In the current work field, new challenges have emerged related to the welding of solid work groups to operate in the online environment. Moreover, through the way of working imposed during the pandemic, the need to overcome spatial barriers and to establish the virtual environment as the main establishment for almost any type of activity was emphasized. This fact has many advantages, if the spatial boundaries are overcome, but many challenges arise, related not only to the adaptation to the proposed technologies, but also requiring a certain conduct of integration within the formed communities.

In the study conducted by Kareem, M.A. and Mijbas, H.A. (2019), they state that only through the techniques implemented by the human resources department can sustain a relationship between organizational effectiveness and dynamic capabilities, so that organizations, in order to achieve organizational effectiveness, need a good HR department human resources to implement learning, response and reconfiguration models for routine work, these representing conditions and capacities for dynamizing the environment.

Through the research carried out by Ahmad, Z., et al., (2021) it was observed that the difference between the human resources practices intended by the organization and those implemented by it, “negatively influences organizational performance, but this fact can be improved by involving employee participation” in the process of implementation and organizational development.

Also, dynamic capabilities can be directly influenced by the entrepreneurial spirit, which was also expressed by Fitriati, T.K. et al., (2020) in their work, dynamic capabilities representing those strategies through which both internal resources and external sources are used through which a company ensures its development and competitiveness.

Moreover, the entrepreneurial spirit, together with a competitive orientation towards the market, represent elements that can influence the degree of sustainability, a fact also emphasized by Rosini, I. and Hakim, D.R. (2021).

The dynamic capabilities established through organizational capabilities are closely correlated with proactivity, innovation, and performance, in the sense that proactivity and innovation influence the performance of companies by promoting and supporting it, a fact expressed by Bature, S.W. et al., (2018) in the conducted study.

Rozak, H.A. et al., (2021) underlines that the change in the organizational system can be done by promoting agile entrepreneurial spirit that can influence dynamic capabilities, in the sense that, through this model, the consolidation and efficiency of the digital ecosystem will be reached.

Dynamic capabilities are based on a quality IT system, directly influencing the innovation process, the production process as well as the marketing process to ensure the performance of small and medium enterprises in the digital era, as shown by Wongwanich B. and Chienwatthanasuk K. (2021) in the study carried out.

Also, for a healthy, long-term development, it is necessary to apply an agile strategic leadership, based on small work teams with strong and dynamic links between their members, which can support innovation, a fact expressed by Chen, X. et al. (2022).

Recent research increasingly proposes the idea of a strategic management, where the central part is occupied by the micro foundations, with their three characteristics, namely, structure, process, and individuals, allowing to move from macro (societal) level to micro (human) level, per individual, which is the main actor for the development of dynamic capabilities, and for that it is necessary to implement a strategic leadership, stated Vera, D. et al. (2022).

In this sense, Chairunisa, F. and Tonapa, J.F., (2022) in their research propose a leader model that agrees generation Y members, being necessary to be a coach in finding solutions and not a manager of his own. Moreover, it is necessary that the tasks can be solved through collaboration, during their fulfillment a positive atmosphere and a motivating framework should be created, and the evaluations should be correct.

Although they are similar in terms of the use of technology, the members of generation Z are different from the members of generation Y, being similar to the members of generation X, who preceded the millennials, who were more anchored in the present time and concretely, having a sense of born of leadership, being more opened to taking risks, finding their personal pleasures more easily in the environment in which they work, as noticed Azhari, A.M. and Pritasari, A. (2022).

If, in the paper: "A model for estimating skills and competencies in Industry 4.0" I proposed a recruitment model based on the competencies required for Industry 4.0, which helps the human resources department by ensuring the optimal teams for each specific project through a recruitment process own to this era of digitization, by following the conception of dedicated execution teams, made up of members of the Y and Z generations who have the necessary skills and abilities, further, we aimed to streamline the production mode through the active and dynamic involvement of human resources, on which we consider a key factor (Suru, S.N. et al., 2020).

Next, in the study: "A model for predicting skills and competencies of Y and Z generation members for Industry 4.0", we sought to prioritize the competencies required for Industry 4.0 by analyzing the strong points of members of the Y and Z generation, and we realized that members of generation Y use social skills, as well as methodological ones, while members of generation Z are more attracted to technical skills and soft skills, which indicates that the latter will prefer a technological or informational update, instead of a face-to-face socialization. Through this approach, we aimed to improve the process of identifying suitable candidates according to their social, methodological, technical, and soft skills (Suru, S.N. et al., 2021)

In his research Sabbagh, M.A. (2021) developed the idea that the learning environment is not the same for everyone, because there are different styles of perception, namely, the visual, the auditory, the kinesthetic and the classical style, which assumes that the basis is taking notes in classes and their assimilation.

Methodology

Through the present research we try to find the answer to the following questions:

- I. In which way organizational performances are correlated to individual skills?
- II. Are the organizational skills affected by the relationship between individual skills and organizational performance?

Our concept is based on the participative management method and aims to discover new methods of making collaborative meetings in the online environment more efficient through psycho-social means of maximum involvement of everyone, regardless of their psychological or sociological profile, following a general model adaptable for all those who are currently present in the educational process, i.e., we target the members of generations X, Y and Z. We also consider it particularly important to capture the current evolution centered on the level of three dimensions, namely:

1. The dynamic skills dimension, which is made up of four other sub-dimensions:
 - a) detection ability,
 - b) learning ability,
 - c) the ability to integrate,
 - d) coordination ability.
2. Level of organizational performance.
3. The dimension of organizational skills.

The model we propose captures all these aspects and is configured for these dimensions, being designed for the organizational societal construct.

To develop the model, we started from the idea of a micro-leadership model based on the Agile system, in which each member of the online team is responsible for the team project. In this sense, each member of the team creates 4 levels of action, namely:

- I. The personal level, where everyone establishes his strengths.
- II. The inter-personal level, where everyone exposes the assimilated knowledge to the group.
- III. The testing stage, where, after testing all participants, it will be observed what gaps in assimilation and communication exist.
- IV. The configuration level, where, following the feedback received from the team, everyone realizes and will improve their assimilation and communication pattern.

These levels are individually configurable, depending on each person, considering the inherent characteristics, as well as the generation they belong to.

Thus, we configured our model according to the following steps, as shown in Fig.1:

- A. Step 1, which is represented by the reconfiguration of the course and teaching method:
 - a) Configure the parts of the course that can be taught visually through diagrams, figures, tables and illustrations, videos, the latter being very important.
 - b) Configure the parts of the course that can be taught aurally, through video sessions and, very importantly, through debates.
 - c) Configure the parts of the course that are supposed to be taught in the classic way by means of preconfigured and commented slides.

- d) The parts of the course to be presented in a practical (kinesthetic) way are configured, the students being placed in practical experiments and preconfigured workshops.

Fig. 1. Logical diagram of the course and learning reconfiguration process

- B. Step 2, the course is configured, and the material is uploaded to the virtual online teaching platform.
- C. Step 3, phase 1, "initiating the personal level": Students select at least two types of teaching, according to their personal preferences, on the condition that they take part in the two types of teaching, which they consider to be more suitable for them well, which means at least 50% of the course.
- D. Step 4, phase 2, "inter-personal level": within this level, learning teams are configured with 3-4 members each, which will be placed in a brainstorming session. For each team, the requirements of a completion project are established, which requires knowledge from all the content of the course, i.e., from the parts taught visually, auditorily, classically, and kinesthetically/practical.
- E. The condition for setting up the teams is that each member has the two chosen types of teaching the course totally different from the other members. In this way, the team is made up of students, who participated and assimilated knowledge from the entire course.

- F. Step 5, phase 3, the "test stage": The project is presented online, by each team, in no more than 15 minutes, and all other teams can participate and ask questions. This represents a testing phase as well as a deepening of the assimilated knowledge, because through the process of assisting other projects, respectively through interactive discussions, the knowledge is deepened. If each team manages to present its project in a clear, coherent logic and with cursive ideas, for the entire topic, it means that the necessary knowledge has been assimilated.
- G. Step 6, phase 4, the "configurational level": After each course, the feedback from the students is sent, along with suggestions for adapting and reconfiguring the course

In our previous work, we developed an operational model of an online group made up of members of generations X, Y and Z, where we proposed for them a type of mixed class for these three generations (Suru, S.N. et al., 2022). In this sense, through this paper we configure a type of mixed class that will contain elements of interest for each of the three present generations. Thus, we structure the course on several dimensions, namely video presentations and practical applications (which are preferred by members of generation Y, who have a preference for visualization), augmented reality and applications (preferred by members of generation Z, who have an advanced kinesthetic preference) to the virtual), and games, interactive tasks and bibliographic bonuses (for members of generation X, who have an inclination towards audition, the face-to-face relational kinesthetic style and the classic style of deepening through diligent study), a model that can be seen structured in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. The mixed class model for members of generations X, Y and Z

Thus, we conclude the realization of some inherent stages:

I. The first phase is that of the personal level, of learning a topic, of your choice, depending on the assimilation method learned, visual, auditory, kinesthetic, or classic, in this stage, members of generations X, Y or Z will internalize the information from course, depending on the channel of communication and assimilation preferred by them. The dynamic skills involved here are detection and learning.

II. The second is represented by the inter-personal level, where the exposure intervenes, through which each tries to relate and explain to the others what he understood, in his own way (visual, auditory, kinesthetic, or classical). The dynamic skills that apply here are those of integration and those of learning.

III. The third phase of the testing stage, is a control phase, in which, with the help of testing, all the knowledge assimilated along the previous stages is verified. The dynamic skills that are applied here are those of coordination, but also those of learning.

IV. The fourth phase of the configuration stage, is the one in which the feedback is received, which will help to improve the assimilation and communication techniques. In this stage, all the four dynamic skills presented are developed, namely those of coordination, learning, detection, and integration (all these are presented in the concept proposed by us through Fig. 3).

In the model shown in Fig. 3, it can be seen how each stage helps to achieve dynamic skills, and the process is a continuous one of dynamism and training for each participant.

Fig. 3. Self-dynamization model within the formal group in the online environment

Discussion and conclusions

Through this paper, we create a feasible model, based on the participatory management method, so that information can be disseminated and assimilated more easily in the online environment, depending on the internalization specifics of each one (visual, auditory, kinesthetic or classic) and the generation of which X, Y or Z is a part, and the collaborative meetings in the online environment should take place in optimal conditions, through psycho-social means of maximum involvement of each individual, they being able to develop and display dynamic skills/capabilities to the maximum. The proposed model is experimental, being configured both following the analyzed studies as well as from the proposals and interviews between teachers and participants. It should be emphasized that the visual, auditory, kinesthetic, or classical teaching methodologies were selected following the proposals of the course participants. It is also worth noting that the primary implementations of this concept were particularly successful, an aspect proven both by the presentation of the final projects and by the information obtained from the feedback given by the participants.

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